

ISAJ NEWSLETTER

An Initiative of ISAJ

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Hokkaido University campus, Sapporo

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<https://isaj.jp>

From Editor's Desk

Greetings and a warm welcome to the third issue of ISAJ Newsletter in 2024!

In this issue, we present you with two research articles, an event report and a photo gallery on the just concluded 15th Annual Symposium.

The Research Spotlight is on discovery of novel inhibitors for Sphingomyelin synthase to control fatty liver disease from plant foods, by Punith. He aims to uncover novel and effective strategies for developing inhibitors to combat obesity and associated disorders.

The Research Highlight is on advancing magnetic storage device technology, where Dr. Rath write about BiFeO₃-based thin films doped with lanthanides, to his newly stated post-doc work on Heat-Assisted Magnetic Recording (HAMR).

ISAJ just held its 15th Annual Symposium on October 29, 2024, at Embassy of India auditorium in Tokyo. See Event Report page and the Photo gallery. ISAJ has reached a milestone with this symposium.

In a first, the Hokkaido Chapter is about to organize ISAJ Hokkaido2024 symposium on December 13, 2024, in the Hokkaido University Sapporo campus.

Our member Ms. Upasana Jhariya of Tohoku University reports winning first prize from Falling Walls in Sendai. Falling Walls Foundation is a global organization that hosts interdisciplinary pitch competitions for early-career professionals. Two pictures of the prize ceremony are given below.

We hope you would find the present issue of our Newsletter interesting. We look forward to receiving your feedback. Any suggestions/ideas for improving the upcoming newsletters are welcome.

Editor(s)
Alok Singh
Aaditya Manjanath

Upasana receiving prize from Falling Walls (below);
ISAJ Hokkaido 2024 Symposium Flyer (right)

**ISAJ Hokkaido 2024 Symposium on
"Collaborative Solutions for a Sustainable World"**

December 13 (Friday), 2024, 9:30 - 17:00
5F Conference Hall, CRIS Building,
North Campus, Hokkaido University

Registration and
Abstract Submission

QR Code

Conveners
Dr. Amrutha A. S.
Dr. Shivakumar K. I.
Dr. Ravindra Raut

Cash Prizes
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Research Institute for Electronic Science
Institute for Chemical Reaction Design and Discovery
Graduate School of Environmental Science

Abstract submission deadline: Nov.15, 2024
Participation Registration deadline: Dec. 1, 2024

ISAJ HOKKAIDO UNIVERSITY

Discovery of novel inhibitors for Sphingomyelin synthase to control fatty liver disease from plant foods

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Punith is a Ph.D. student at Hokkaido University, Japan. His research focusses on the identification of potent inhibitors for the sphingomyelin synthase (SMS) enzyme through the extraction and characterization of natural products to control obesity. By integrating *in-vitro* techniques with *in-silico* approaches like molecular docking and dynamics simulations, he aims to uncover novel and effective strategies for developing inhibitors to combat obesity.

Introduction

Obesity, characterized by excessive fat accumulation that poses significant risks to health, has become one of the most critical public health challenges of the 21st century. Defined by a body mass index (BMI) of 30 or higher, it is a multifaceted condition driven by genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors. Over recent decades, obesity has transformed from a localized health concern into a global epidemic, with its prevalence rising sharply across all demographics [1].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 1 billion people worldwide were obese as of 2022, including 650 million adults, 340 million adolescents, and 39 million children. While obesity rates remain highest in high-income countries, the rapid urbanization and economic development of middle- and low-income nations have led to

an alarming surge in cases, especially in urban regions. This global trend is fueled by the widespread adoption of sedentary lifestyles and diets rich in processed foods, sugar, and unhealthy fats [2].

The increasing prevalence of obesity is accompanied by a rise in associated metabolic disorders, such as fatty liver disease, type 2 diabetes, and cardiovascular complications. These health concerns highlight the urgent need for innovative therapeutic interventions. One promising avenue lies in targeting sphingomyelin synthases (SMS1 and SMS2), enzymes that play a central role in lipid metabolism. These enzymes catalyze the transfer of a phosphorylcholine group to ceramide, forming sphingomyelin as shown in Figure 1. Overexpression of SMS enzymes has been implicated in obesity and lipid-related disorders, making them attractive targets for therapeutic development [3].

Fig. 1 Role of Sphingomyelin synthase (SMS) in production of Sphingomyelin.

Natural products, renowned for their structural diversity and biological activity, have long served as a foundation for drug discovery. Marine algae, such as *Sargassum fusiforme* (commonly known as hijiki), have drawn attention as a rich source of bioactive compounds, including fatty acids and polysaccharides, which exhibit diverse pharmacological properties. Investigating hijiki and other marine resources for potential SMS inhibitors could pave the way for novel, natural therapies to combat obesity and its related metabolic disorders.

Workflow

To identify potent SMS inhibitors, we are employing a stepwise approach that begins with *in-vitro* techniques and is complemented by *in-silico* validation. The *in-vitro* phase involves screening natural compounds to evaluate their inhibitory effects on SMS1 and SMS2 enzymes by using SMS inhibition assay previously developed by our group [4]. These assays yield critical experimental data, such as IC₅₀ values, inhibition rates, and enzyme specificity, offering direct evidence of a compound's efficacy. Additionally, cytotoxicity assays are conducted to ensure that candidate compounds do not exhibit adverse effects on cell viability.

Following the *in-vitro* screening, *in-silico* techniques are employed to validate and further investigate the identified compounds. Computational methods such as molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations are used to predict how these compounds interact with SMS enzymes at the molecular level. These studies provide insights into binding affinities, key molecular interactions, and the stability of the enzyme-inhibitor complexes. By cross-referencing the computational predictions with experimental data, we can confirm the reliability of the identified inhibitors and refine their potential as

therapeutic agents.

This integrated approach starting with *in-vitro* assays and reinforcing findings with *in-silico* techniques not only ensures the robustness of the discovery process but also provides a comprehensive understanding of the interactions between SMS enzymes and natural inhibitors. By focusing on natural products like hijiki, this strategy holds significant promise for developing targeted therapies to combat obesity and its associated metabolic disorders.

References

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Advancing Magnetic Storage Device Technology for a Sustainable Future

Dr. Soumyaranjan Ratha

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Presently a post-doc at the National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), Japan, Dr. Rath received his PhD in Materials Science and was a post-doc at Akita University, Japan. His Ph.D. and subsequent research focuses on understanding and manipulating magnetic properties in the thin films for innovative applications in advanced magnetic storage devices and energy-efficient spintronic technologies.

Introduction

The demand for energy-efficient, high-performance magnetic storage devices is soaring amid rapid technological advancement. As Society 5.0 and the IoT-driven future take shape, the need for eco-friendly IT equipment is critical. Magnetic devices, essential for information recording, displays, and sensing, are major power consumers, posing a challenge to meet the energy demands of integrated systems. Magnetic storage devices rely on magnetization reversal, spin injection, and tunnel magnetoresistance, all requiring current flow. Increased integration drives higher power consumption, demanding new approaches. Developing novel mate-

rials and methods can enable low-power magnetic devices while enhancing performance.

In my doctoral research, I focused on the potential of ferromagnetic and ferroelectric materials, particularly BiFeO₃-based thin films, to enable low-power, high-performance magnetic devices like racetrack memory, magnetic sensor and magnetic optical devices as shown in Figure 1. These materials offer the unique ability to control both magnetization and electric polarization through the application of electric fields, which provides a more energy-efficient alternative to current current-driven methods. By incorporating different lanthanide elements such as

Figure 1 Application of multiferroic thin films in magnetic devices.

Figure 2 Comparison of coercivity change between etched area (out of dot) and etched (on dot) area of BiFeO₃-based thin films in RIE condition (with and without oxygen presence).

La, Nd, and Eu, I successfully synthesized thin films with enhanced magnetic properties, including high saturation magnetization (M_s), large perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (K_u), and significant magnetic Kerr rotation angles (Θ_k). These improvements not only make these thin films more effective for device applications but also enable power-efficient control over the magnetization process [1].

In addition to optimizing the magnetic properties, I also investigated the durability of these thin films under micro-element processing conditions essential for device fabrication. Using methods like reactive ion etching, I was able to identify processing conditions that minimized damage to the films, such as suppressing oxygen vacancy formation by employing a mixed gas of CHF₃ and oxygen, as shown in Figure 2 [2]. This is crucial for maintaining the integrity and functionality of these films during device formation and packaging.

HAMR Media

Currently as a postdoctoral researcher I am working on HDD/HAMR Media. Hard Disk Drives (HDDs) remain essential for cost-effective, reliable data storage, serving personal and enterprise needs. However, surging data generation demands higher capacities at lower costs. Current perpendicular magnetic recording (PMR) technology is nearing its physical limits, restricting storage density improvements without risking data integrity or reliability.

The challenge lies in the fact that as storage density increases, the magnetic grains used to store data become smaller and more prone to thermal instability. This increases the risk of data loss and makes it harder to maintain performance at higher areal densities. In order to continue pushing the boundaries of storage capacity, new recording techniques are necessary. One promising solution that has emerged to overcome these limitations is Heat-Assisted Magnetic Recording (HAMR). HAMR utilizes a laser to heat a small area of the disk just before data is written, temporarily reducing the coercivity of the magnetic material. This allows for the creation of much smaller magnetic grains, which can be densely packed, without the risk of thermal instability or data corruption. As a result, HAMR enables significantly higher storage capacities, potentially up to 50 terabytes (TB) on a single drive. This breakthrough not only increases storage density but also ensures data integrity, making HAMR a game-changer in the storage industry.

HAMR faces challenges in maximizing storage density, with dual-layer HAMR emerging as a key advancement. By incorporating two magnetic recording layers in a single disk, it effectively doubles storage capacity while maintaining data integrity and thermal stability, as shown in Figure 3. Magnetization is independently controlled, and a laser precisely targets the lower layer for writing without affecting the upper layer. This enables a significant increase in areal density without compromising drive performance or reliability.

Conventional (2-level) recording

Next-generation (multi-level) recording

Figure 3 Schematic of the concept of multi-level magnetic recording compared to current 2-level magnetic recording technology in hard disk drives.

The importance of dual-layer HAMR lies not only in its potential to significantly increase storage capacity but also in its ability to make data storage more sustainable. As the demand for storage continues to grow, dual-layer HAMR can help reduce the physical space and energy consumption needed for data storage solutions [3]. By enabling higher capacity on fewer drives, it minimizes the environmental impact of data centres, which are significant consumers of energy. Additionally, fewer drives mean a reduction in the raw materials required for manufacturing, helping to address issues related to electronic

waste.

References

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15th ISAJ Annual Symposium-2024 “Transformative Technologies for a Sustainable Future”

Conveners: Dr. Sahiba Bano*, Dr. Deeksha Arya**
and Dr. Aaditya Manjanath*,

*National Institute for Materials Science, Japan, **University of Tokyo

The 15th Indian Scientists' Association in Japan (ISAJ) Annual Symposium on “Transformative Technologies for a Sustainable Future” was organized on 29th October 2024 at Embassy of India auditorium in Tokyo, Japan. This event marked the 15th anniversary of ISAJ and coincided with Ayurveda Day celebrations.

We received an overwhelming response for participation – invited as well as contributory. The symposium hosted 5 Plenary Talks, 14 Invited Talks, and more than 30 Poster Presentations by researchers associated with various academic and research institutions from the Kantō (Tōkyō, Tsukuba, Yokosuka, Kawasaki, Isehara), Chūbu (Shizuoka, Iwata, Niigata), Kansai (Kyōto), Kyūshū (Kitakyūshū), Tōhoku (Akita, Sendai), and Hokkaidō (Sapporo) regions of Japan.

The symposium was opened with an encouraging talk by His Excellency Mr. Sibi George, Ambassador of India to Japan, who emphasized the cooperation between our two countries. The symposium brought together eminent researchers, professors, early-career researchers and students from diverse fields of science and technology including but not limited to materials science, renewable energy, medicine, seismology, environmental science, quantum photonics, music generation, data science, and food science. The sessions were planned to be multidisciplinary in nature to allow experts and young researchers from diverse backgrounds to share their expertise, thereby providing a unique opportunity to learn outside of their specialized domains and to innovate their ideas and research outcomes for the benefit of science and society.

Plenary talks covered cutting edge research on a wide range of topics: thermoelectric materials and devices for waste heat power generation, sustainable urban digital twin with computational urban

management, coastal conservation and sustainable coastal development, multiscale simulation for designing structural materials, and data driven materials research. Wider ranging research areas were also covered in other talks, relating to nutrition, medicinal drugs, quantum photonics, environment, etc.

The abstracts book can be downloaded from ISAJ website.

Four Best Poster Presentation Awards were presented, as in the previous years, (a certificate and shopping coupons worth 25,000 yen each) for the encouragement of young researchers and students. The awardees were Dr. Anjaneyulu Dirisala, Mr. Punith M. Sundaraswamy, Dr. Poonam Rani, and Ms. Samridhi P. Mishra. Presentation of the awards was conducted in a special program organized by the Embassy on the Ayurveda Day. The awards were presented by the Speaker of the Legislative Assembly of Odisha state of India, Ms. Surama Padhy, in the presence of His Excellency the Ambassador Mr. Sibi George. We would like to congratulate the awardees for their wonderful presentations!

The symposium was a grand success thanks to the efforts invested by the organizing team of ISAJ as well as the staff at Embassy of India in Tokyo. Special thanks to Dr. Yashawant Dev Panwar (Counselor, Science & Technology) and Ms. Kiyō Endō for providing us the necessary support in ensuring the symposium proceeded seamlessly. We would also like to thank all the participants for responding to our invitations readily.

The symposium was generously supported by our donor Sai Hira India Foundation, main sponsor The Indian Commerce and Industry Association Japan, and sponsors Forecast Ocean Plus, Inc., and Ambika Japan.

We hope to see you in the next Annual Symposium of ISAJ!

15th ISAJ Annual Symposium-2024

The reception

His Excellency Mr. Sibi George, Ambassador of India, keynote

Conveners' address

the audience

... break times...

... and the lively poster session!

15th Annual Symposium of ISAJ held on 29th October 2024
in VCC Auditorium of the Embassy of India in Tokyo
His Excellency the Ambassador Mr. Sibi George is in the center.

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About ISAJ

The Indian Scientists' Association in Japan (ISAJ) is a Non-Profit Organization (NPO) aimed at networking and promoting Science and Technology Cooperation between India and Japan.

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